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NON-PLANAR MULTINOZZLE ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING OF THERMOSET COMPOSITES

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Jean-François Chauvette, PhD

Laboratory of multiscale mechanics

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Chaires de recherche
du Canada

MOTIVATION

- Additive Manufacturing (AM) / 3D printing in the aerospace industry

Lighter parts

Reduction of material losses

Flexibility for complex geometry

Relativity Space 3D-printed Terran 1 rocket
(wsj.com, 2023)

Aircraft gas turbine engine
(www.safran-group.com)

- Investigation of AM for fabricating abradable thermosetting composite coatings
 - Multifunctional capability
 - ACARE (Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe) standards¹
 - 55% reduction of CO₂ emission by 2030 and net-zero by 2050
 - 65% reduction in perceived noise by 2050

SELECTED ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING CONCEPTS

- Layer-by-layer fabrication
- Direct Ink Writing (DIW)
 - Material extrusion technique
 - Viscoelastic inks, room temperature
 - Microscaffolds
 - Popular application for tissue engineering
 - Potential for sound absorption
 - Multinozzle printhead
- 6-axis robot for AM
 - Non-planar
 - Large-scale

Schematics of layer-by-layer material extrusion (adapted from Nisja et al., 2021)

DIW of a microstructure (Therriault et al., 2005)

Multinozzle DIW (Kranz, 2013)

Schematic of 6-axis robot (Fanuc America Corporation, 2018)

3D-printed bridge (Striatum project, ETH Zürich, 2021)

PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION & OBJECTIVE

- Main challenges
 - DIW of thermosetting microcaffolds
 - **Small-scale** applications
 - 6-axis robots for large-scale AM
 - Mostly **single nozzle** non-planar AM
 - **Long printing times** with high resolution (e.g., up to days).
 - Current multinozzle printhead technologies
 - Relatively **low flow rates** and low viscosity material.
 - No report of **non-planar multinozzle AM** with complete freedom of printhead orientation.
- General objective

Develop a non-planar multinozzle AM approach using a 6-axis robot to achieve large-scale manufacturing of high-resolution thermosetting microcaffolds

6-AXIS ROBOT AM INFRASTRUCTURE

- AM workflow and experimental setup

PLANAR PRINTING CASE STUDIES

- Pressure prediction : **Multinozzle Extrusion Prediction Model (MEPM)**

- Predicting for printing speed $v = 50 - 250$ mm/s
- ΔP recorded using Wika A-10 sensor + Labview

$$(1) \eta_{app,i} = K \dot{\gamma}_i^{n-1}$$

$$(2) R_i = \frac{128 L \eta_{app,i}}{\pi D^4} \left(\frac{3+1/n}{4} \right)$$

$$(3) \Delta P = R_{eq} \sum_{i=1}^{\alpha} Q_i$$

Case studies pressure prediction using organic ink

- Material : Organic ink¹

PLANAR PRINTING CASE STUDIES

- High-speed printing of microsc scaffold network
 - Network of 9×15 microsc scaffolds (generated with each printing passes)
 - $\Delta P = 4.75 \text{ MPa}$, $v = \mathbf{250 \text{ mm/s}}$ ($Q_{\text{tot}} = 319 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}$)

- 5 layers (1 mm thick), 234×390 printed filaments
- Printing time = **1 min 30 s** (vs. 41 min with single nozzle)
 - 3 times faster than previously published work for similar results¹

PLANAR PRINTING CASE STUDIES

- Thick partitioned microsc scaffold network
 - 3 × 3 network + walls
 - 50 layers** (10 mm), 78 × 78 filaments
 - $\Delta P = 2.40 \text{ MPa}$, $v = 50 \text{ mm/s}$ ($Q_{\text{tot}} = 63.2 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}$)
 - $t = 8 \text{ min } 45 \text{ s}$

X-ray micro-CT scanned volume
(following epoxy encapsulation)

b) Cross-section A - A

c)

Cross-section B - B

$z_2 = 422 \mu\text{m}$
 $z_1 = 294 \mu\text{m}$
 $s_1 = 614 \mu\text{m}$
 $s_2 = 1449 \mu\text{m}$

Cross-section C - C

THERMOSETTING POLYMER MATERIAL

- Preparation and mixing¹

DAC 330-100 SE SpeedMixer

- Viscosity characterization
 - Shear-thinning behavior

NON-PLANAR MICROSCAFFOLD GENERATION

- Python program : **Multinozzle Toolpath Generator (MTG)**
- Input = surface scan mesh, multinozzle config., network definition, printing parameters
- Output = **non-planar multinozzle AM trajectory** for 6-axis robots
- **Collision avoidance** between nozzles and substrate

Step 1 : NURBS parametrization

Step 2 : Toolpath generation + projection

Found clearance
 $\Delta z_{\max} = 24.2D$ (material specific)

NON-PLANAR MICROSCAFFOLD NETWORKS

- Surface of aircraft casing with double curvature
 - 5×15 network, 20 layers
 - $v = 50$ mm/s, $\Delta P = \sim 6 \rightarrow 9$ MPa
 - $t = 20$ min (vs. 8.5 h with single nozzle)

3D scan of
 $\frac{1}{4}$ casing

MTG

Timelapse video of non-planar multinozzle AM on aircraft casing

NON-PLANAR MICROSCAFFOLD NETWORKS

- Surface of aircraft casing with double curvature

- Error $\bar{d} = 1.5 \%$
- Error $\bar{p} = 0.7 \%$
- Error $\bar{z} = 2.4 \%$

- Distance comparison with programmed toolpath¹
 - Recorded toolpath using DigiMetric Labview Fanuc library
 - 17,196 recorded points
 - 95% below saturation (0.020 mm)
 - Worst zone error = 15 μm (6 % of D)

ABRADABLE THERMOSETTING COMPOSITE

- Preparation and mixing¹

Modification of **commercial
abradable resin (EC-3524)**

SpeedMixer

~250 cm³ (320 g)

3D-printable highly viscous **abradable
thermosetting composite**

- Viscosity characterization

Abradable :

$$K = 6,673 \text{ Pa s}^n$$

$$n = 0.3578$$

EPON 828 :

$$K = 10,120 \text{ Pa s}^n$$

$$n = 0.2429$$

6-AXIS NON-PLANAR MULTIPROCESS AM

Step 1

Non-planar FFF of thermoplastic sandwich panel ($\times 4$).

Nozzle $D = 0.4 \text{ mm}$, $v = 15 \text{ mm/s}$,
 $\sim 60 \text{ h.}^1$

Step 2

Non-planar multinozzle toolpath over FFF part

Step 3

Non-planar multinozzle AM of 3D-printable abradable material on top of thermoplastic sandwich panel.
 $v = 50 \text{ mm/s}$, $\Delta P = 9 \rightarrow 18 \text{ MPa}$, $t \sim 40 \text{ min}$.

6-AXIS NON-PLANAR MULTIPROCESS AM

- Aircraft component demonstrator
 - Bottom level : 3 × 19 network
 - 16 layers, $p = 750 \mu\text{m}$ (3.2 % error)
 - Top level : 7 × 45 network
 - 14 layers, $p = 184 \mu\text{m}$ (4.3 % error)
 - $t \sim 40 \text{ min}$ vs. $\sim 20\text{h}$ with single nozzle
 - 1/12 circumference (proof of concept)
 - Multifunctional (abradable + acoustic)

Last layer top view

Top porosity level

Bottom porosity level

CONCLUSION

Develop a non-planar multinozzle AM approach using a 6-axis robot to achieve large-scale manufacturing of high-resolution thermosetting microcaffolds

1. Investigate high-speed multinozzle additive manufacturing

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.102294>

- Open source Multinozzle Extrusion Prediction Model (MEPM)¹
- ΔP prediction error = 3 %
- $v = 250$ mm/s (3× faster than literature)

1. <https://github.com/lm2-poly/mepm>
2. <https://github.com/lm2-poly/mtg>

2. Expand the development of non-planar multinozzle additive manufacturing

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110627>

- Open source Multinozzle Toolpath Generator (MTG)²
- 6-DOF multinozzle orientation
- Toolpath error = 15 μm (6 % of D)

3. Study the multiprocess multinozzle additive manufacturing of an aircraft component demonstrator

<https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202300399>

- Multinozzle AM of highly viscous abrasible composite
- Large-scale DIW integration into multiprocess AM
- Multilevel p max error = 4.3 %

**Thank you
for your attention !**

Industrial partners

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composites à haute performance

APPENDIX: EXTRA SLIDES

ABRADABLE SEAL COATINGS

- Seal coatings to prevent air leaks
 - Allow small clearances of rotating parts

Schematic of abraded seal coating (adapted from Salvat et al., 2013)

Cross section view of gas turbine engine (aerobuzz.fr)

- AM of abradable thermosetting coating
 - Microscaffolds with sound absorption potential

AM proof of concept of abradable microscuffold (Dubourg-Cassagne, 2015)

High-speed AM of abradable microscuffold for sound absorption (Brzeski et al., 2021)

- Planar slicing
 - CAD model is tessellated in a triangle mesh
 - Layers are "sliced" by intersecting planes with the mesh
 - G-code is generated according to the printing parameters

Schematic of FFF (Elkaseer et al., 2020)

CAD model (.STL file)

Layers slicing

Layer-by-layer 3D printing

- Non-planar slicing (three selected techniques)

Cylindrical projection (Zhao et al., 2018)

Mesh outline offset (Huang et Singamneni, 2015)

Inclined layer slicing (Zhao et al., 2018)

- Basic concepts and motion principles
 - Kinematic chain, joints
 - Tool Center Point (TCP)
- Potential for AM
 - Non-planar material extrusion
 - Large-scale builds

a) Schematics of non-planar slicing, b) Nozzle orientation (adapted from Chen et al., 2019)

3D-printed bridge (Striatus project, ETH Zürich, 2021)

- Robotic additive manufacturing system for dynamic build orientations¹
 - Study of gravity effect on FFF
 - Surface roughness measurement on underside of overhanging sections

e)

Our investigation of FFF printer orientation effects is, to the best of our knowledge, the first quantitative assessment of the effect of printing at different orientations relative to gravity. **Somewhat counterintuitively, we find that gravitational orientation has no impact.** This is an important finding in the context of MAAM because it means that both the extruder and build tray can be rotated as necessary to maximize workspace and optimize kinematics.

Authors	Highlights	Image
<p>Khalil et al. (2005)</p> <p>Khalil and Sun (2007)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 independent nozzles, different materials Flow rate of 0.51 $\mu\text{L/s}$ Printing speed of 15 mm/s 	
<p>Hansen et al. (2013)</p> <p>Kranz (2013)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 64 nozzles of 200 μm wide Machined in PMMA block Printing of 0.38 m^2 4-layer micro scaffold in 25 min at printing speed of 40 mm/s 	
<p>Skylar-Scott et al. (2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 16 nozzles of 250 μm inner diameter Printing speed of 40 mm/s Multimaterial shifting frequency of 50 Hz 	

Authors	Highlights	Image
<p>Yoon et al. (2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 FFF extruders for independent extrusion (E3D volcano) Mounted on 6-axis robot Variable resolution (0.15 – 0.8 mm) 	
<p>Baca and Ahmad (2020)</p> <p>Mhatre (2019)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 FFF extruders for simultaneous extrusion (E3D Kraken) Printing speed of 17 mm/s Variable resolution (0.15 – 0.8 mm) 	
<p>Uzel et al. (2022)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-planar multi-nozzle AM Variable nozzle height Printing speed of 5 mm/s Printing in one direction, adaptable to the substrate scanned topography 	

- Characterization of process-related apparent viscosity
 - Organic ink (Therriault et al., 2005)
 - 10 → 40 wt% microcrystalline wax (SP 18, Strahl & Pitsch)
 - 90 → 60 wt% petroleum jelly (Chesebrough-Pond's)
 - Non-Newtonian fluid (shear-thinning)

<p>Apparent viscosity</p> $\eta_{app} = \frac{\tau_W}{\dot{\gamma}_W}$	<p>Shear stress</p> $\tau_W = \frac{P_{appl} - P_a}{2(L/R)}$
<p>Shear rate</p> $\dot{\gamma}_W = \frac{4Q}{\pi R^3} \left(\frac{3+b}{4} \right)$ <p style="text-align: center;">$\dot{\gamma}_{Newt}$</p>	<p>Rabinowitsch correction</p> $b = \frac{d \log(\dot{\gamma}_{Newt})}{d \log(\tau_W)}$

Characterization of process-related apparent viscosity (Bruneaux et al., 2008)

Power-law model for viscosity¹ (GNF)

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}) = m\dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$$

Hagen-Poiseuille law¹

$$Q = \frac{\pi(P_0 - P_L)R^4}{8\mu L}$$

Carreau-Yasuda model¹

$$\frac{\eta(\dot{\gamma}) - \eta_\infty}{\eta_0 - \eta_\infty} = [1 + (\dot{\gamma}\lambda)^a]^{\frac{n-1}{a}}$$

Pressure gradient calculation

Apparent viscosity (η_{app})

Pressure gradient (ΔP)

$$(1) Q_i = v A_{nozzle}$$

$$(4) R_i = \frac{128 L \eta_{app,i} \left(\frac{3+1/n}{4}\right)}{\pi D^4}$$

$$(2) \dot{\gamma}_i = \frac{32 Q_i \left(\frac{3+1/n}{4}\right)}{\pi D^3}$$

$$(5) R_{eq} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^{\alpha} \frac{1}{R_i}} \text{ (for nozzles in parallel)}$$

$$(3) \eta_{app,i} = K \dot{\gamma}_i^{n-1}$$

$$(6) \Delta P = R_{eq} \sum_{i=1}^{\alpha} Q_i$$

K : Consistency index (Pa.sⁿ)
 n : Power-law index (-)
($n < 1$ for shear-thinning fluid)

α : Number of nozzles

Total volumetric flow rate calculation

$$(7) Q_{i,guess} = Q_i$$

Find new R_i with **imperfect** nozzles

$$(8) Q_{i,new} = \frac{\Delta P}{R_i}$$

$$(9) \Delta Q_i = \frac{|Q_{i,new} - Q_{i,guess}|}{Q_{i,guess}} < 10^{-4} ?$$

No

$$(10) Q_{i,guess} = Q_{i,new}$$

Yes

$$(11) Q_{tot} = \sum_{i=1}^{\alpha} Q_{i,new}$$

- Flow resistance equation

- Hagen-Poiseuille flow rate of Newtonian fluid in pressure-driven flow in a pipe :

$$(1) \quad v(r) = \frac{(P_0 - P_L)(R^2 - r^2)}{4\eta L}$$

$$(2) \quad Q = v_{eff} A$$

$$(3) \quad Q = \frac{(P_0 - P_L)R^2}{4\eta L} \cdot \frac{\pi R^2}{2}$$

$$(4) \quad Q = \frac{\pi(P_0 - P_L)R^4}{8\eta L}$$

$$(5) \quad \frac{Q8\eta L}{\pi R^4} = (P_0 - P_L)$$

$$(6) \quad \Delta P = \frac{128\eta L}{\pi D^4} Q = RQ$$

- For non-Newtonian fluid, we must add the Rabinowitsch correction :

$$(7) \quad \Delta P = \left(\frac{3+1/n}{4}\right) \frac{128\eta L}{\pi D^4} Q$$

$$(8) \quad R = \left(\frac{3+1/n}{4}\right) \frac{128\eta L}{\pi D^4}$$

- Can also be obtained using the definition of viscosity :

$$(1) \quad \eta = \frac{\tau}{\dot{\gamma}}$$

$$(4) \quad \eta = \frac{\pi R^4}{8LQ} \Delta P$$

$$(2) \quad \eta = \frac{\frac{\Delta P}{2L/R}}{\frac{4Q}{\pi R^3}}$$

$$(5) \quad \Delta P = \frac{8LQ}{\pi R^4} \eta$$

$$(6) \quad \Delta P = \frac{8\eta L}{\pi R^4} Q = \frac{128\eta L}{\pi D^4} Q$$

$$(3) \quad \eta = \frac{\Delta P \pi R^3}{\frac{L}{2R} 4Q}$$

$$(7) \quad \Delta P = \left(\frac{3+1/n}{4}\right) \frac{128\eta L}{\pi D^4} Q$$

- Matlab program for multinozzle extrusion prediction
 - Input = printing speed (v), material viscosity parameters (K, n), nozzle geometry (D, L, α)
 - Output = required pressure (ΔP), total volumetric flow rate (Q_{tot})
 - Organic ink

a) Validation with organic ink¹ and dissolved PLA² (single nozzle), b), c), d) Exploration of multinozzle configurations

- Simulation of clogged nozzles
 - Organic ink, $v = 50$ mm/s
 - Nozzle diameter = 0 mm
 - Reservoir piston speed is unchanged

Simulation of clogged nozzles using the MEPM. Clogged nozzles are simulated by setting their diameter to zero.

MICROSCAFFOLD NETWORK TYPICAL GEOMETRY

- Large partitioned microscaffold network

- 9 × 15 network
- $\Delta P = 2.40 \text{ MPa}$
- $v = 50 \text{ mm/s}$
- $Q_{\text{tot}} = 63.2 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}$
- 8 min 45 s

- 9 × 10⁴ mm²
- 5 layers
- Wall features

- Slow-down
- Desynchronization of motion and extrusion**
- Over-extrusion

Programmed toolpath

- Variable pore size microscaffold network

- 3 × 5 network
- $v = 50 \text{ mm/s}$
- 2 layers
- theta increase**

$$p_{\text{theo}} = s \cdot \cos\theta - d$$

θ	p_{theo} (μm)	\bar{p} (μm)	Error (%)
0	750	736	2
30	616	606	2
45	457	436	5
60	250	233	7
75.5	0	0	-

- MTG V5.6, 2023
- Single curvature sinusoidal surface
 - Max $\Delta z = 2.2D$ (limit $\Delta z = 24.2D$)
 - Uneven spacing due to toolpath distortion

- Limit $\Delta z = 24.2D$
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VeQNQTJUrb4>
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sd902JQLBzU>

$$\Delta z = h + D$$

- Substrate topography acquisition
 - Challenge : experimental reference frame calibration
 - Sinusoidal surface : validation of the non-planar AM method

Step 1 : Non-planar surface scan

Step 2 : Mesh reference frame creation

Step 3 : Experimental reference frame creation

- Single curvature sinusoidal surface

- Abradable material formulations development process map¹
 - Using hydrophilic fumed silica (Evonik Aerosil 200)

(b)

(c)

(d)

- Summary of materials used in this research project

Material	Composition	Density (g/cm ³)	Power law parameters
Organic ink	60 wt% petroleum jelly 40 wt% microcrystalline wax	0.905	$K = 604 \text{ Pa s}^n$ $n = 0.468$
Epon formulation	10 wt. part Epon 828 resin 4 wt. part Epikure 3274 curing agent 14 wt.% hydrophilic fumed silica	1.214	$K = 10,120 \text{ Pa s}^n$ $n = 0.2429$
Abradable formulation ¹	94 wt. part EC-3524 Part A (neat curing agent) 100 wt. part EC-3524 Part B (neat resin) 12 wt.% hydrophobic fumed silica	1.279	$K = 6,673 \text{ Pa s}^n$ $n = 0.3578$

- Collision avoidance (TCP offset from surface)
- Pore size adjustment across the layers

Avoid nozzles collision with the curved surface (offset h)

$$h = R - \sqrt{R^2 - x^2}$$

R : surface radius
 x : multinozzle $\frac{1}{2}$ width
 h : tool offset to avoid collision
 \circ : filament ($d = 250 \mu\text{m}$)

For example:

Curved surface
 $R = 1 \text{ m}$
 $h = 78 \mu\text{m}$

Adjust inter-filament distance p for each layer

Non-adjusted distance $p = p'$

Adjusted distance $p > p'$

- Pore size variation across the layers using variable θ

- θ calculation as function of local radius

- Pore size p calculation

$$(1) \beta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{W_1}{2 \cdot r_{\text{local}}} \right)$$

$$(4) \delta\theta_i = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{W_i}{W} \right) - \theta_{i-1}$$

$$(6) p_i = s \cos\theta - d$$

$$(2) r_i = r_{\text{local}} \pm z_i$$

$$(5) \theta_i = \theta_{i-1} + \delta\theta_i$$

$$(7) p_i = (p + d) \left(\frac{r_{\text{local}} \pm z_i}{r_{\text{local}}} \right) - d$$

$$(3) W_i = 2 \cdot r_i \cdot \tan(\beta)$$

- Assembly error sources
 - Two interfaces assembled with screws
 - No locating pins
 - Unknown θ error

Reservoir assembly ($\times 2$ screws)

Printhead assembly ($\times 4$ screws)

Target $p = 750$ μm				
Target θ ($^\circ$)	θ ($^\circ$)	p (mm)	Error p (mm)	Error p (%)
0	0	0.750		
Error θ ($^\circ$)				
+ 7.1	7.1	0.742	0.008	1.02%
- 7.1	-7.1	0.742	0.008	1.02%
+ 2.0	2.0	0.749	0.001	0.08%
- 2.0	-2.0	0.749	0.001	0.08%

Target $p = 184$ μm				
Target θ ($^\circ$)	θ ($^\circ$)	p (mm)	Error p (mm)	Error p (%)
64.28	64.28	0.184		
Error θ ($^\circ$)				
+ 0.5	64.78	0.176	0.008	4.28%
- 0.5	63.78	0.192	-0.008	-4.26%
+ 2.0	66.28	0.152	0.032	17.23%
- 2.0	62.28	0.215	-0.031	-16.95%

- Aircraft component as a lightweight part : density comparison
 - Benchmark : helium gas pycnometer¹
 - Microscaffold : estimated apparent density
 - thermoplastic (PEEK CF30): from datasheet
 - Typical aluminum alloys used for aircraft : $\rho \sim 2.7 \text{ g/cm}^3$

Density of benchmark and parts of the aircraft component demonstrator

Part	p (μm)	Density ρ (g/cm^3)
Benchmark material (commercial EC-3524)	-	0.505
Abradable printable formulation	-	1.279
Bottom porosity level	750	0.346
Top porosity level	184	0.735
Overall microscaffold (both levels)	750, 184	0.535
PEEK CF30 material (sandwich panel)	-	1.380

MICROSCAFFOLD APPARENT DENSITY

1. Estimate the mass of each porosity level
 - Multiply the abrasable formulation bulk density (1.279 g/cm³) to volumed of printed filaments
2. Divided the estimated mass by overall volume occupied by the microscaffold network

Multinozzle printhead		
α	26	nozzles
d	0.25	mm
A	0.049	mm ²

overall dimensions		Unit
L	520	mm
l	78	mm
t	5.6	mm
vol	227136	mm ³
	227.1	cm ³

level 1	p750							
nb layers	16	nb pass	nb fila/layer	nb fila tot	long (mm)	vol (mm ³)		
rows	19		494	3952	78	15131		
cols	3		78	624	520	15928		
thick	2.83	mm		4576		31059	mm ³	31.1 cm ³
vol eff	114785	mm ³				14%	du vol tot	39.7 g
	114.8	cm ³						0.346 g/cm ³

level 2	p184							
nb layers	14	nb pass	nb fila/layer	nb fila tot	long (mm)	vol (mm ³)		
rows	45		1170	8190	78	31358		
cols	7		182	1274	520	32519		
thick	2.74	mm		9464		63877	mm ³	63.9 cm ³
vol eff	111134	mm ³				28%	du vol tot	81.7 g
	111.1	cm ³						0.735 g/cm ³

Level 1 + 2		Vol tot	94937	mm ³
Nb filaments tot	14040		94.9	cm ³
		Masse tot	121.4	g
		apparent density	0.535	g/cm ³
		(level avg)	0.541	g/cm ³
		error	1.1%	

- Abradability characterization¹

Experimental setup of the **abrasion test** mimicking an engine (Safran, France).

Benchmark samples (molded block of EC-3524)

Molded benchmark samples using hand spatula.

3D-printed samples using single nozzle. $v = 80 \text{ mm/s}$, $\Delta P = 2.7 - 5.10 \text{ MPa}$, **30 min.**

- Abradability characterization¹

